

EXPLORING TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE HANDLING MULTIPLE ANCILLARY FUNCTIONS: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Abstract: This study utilized a multiple case design to describe and gain insights from the performances of teachers handling multiple ancillary functions in South Fatima District under the City Schools Division of General Santos City, Philippines. This study used an in-depth interview to gather the data needed. Findings of the study revealed six different cases of the participants such as elementary school teacher 1 as the passionate and committed; elementary school teacher 2 as the versatile and diligent; elementary school teacher 3 as the strategic and proud teacher; while secondary school teacher 1 as the ever-patient and job-oriented; secondary school teacher 2 as the eager to serve with integrity and being optimistic; and secondary school teacher 3 as the loving and selfless teacher. The study implied that these teachers entails life-long commitment in order to perform well despite of handling multiple ancillary functions. It was a complete package on sacrifice, persistence and determination. Handling multiple ancillary functions means being prepared holistically, aside from being optimistic and determined; they should also need to be strategic.

Keywords: Teachers' performance, multiple ancillary functions, multiple case analysis, educational management, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

“Teaching is one of the noblest professions. It requires adequate preparation and training, patience, devotion, and a deep sense of responsibility. Those who mold the human mind have wrought not for time, but eternity.” -*Calvin Coolidge*.

The above passage explains that teachers are responsible for shaping human minds holistically; their duties and responsibilities do not end on preparing lesson plans, administering grading tests, and documenting learners' progress, but most especially on propagating each human soul that lasts for a lifetime. It is a fact that teachers' job is beyond the four corners of the classroom since learning happens everywhere wherein the learners gain experience. This aspect demands the teachers to render exigencies on the service, requiring the teachers to spend more than the regular working hours, and in worse cases, demand teachers out of their time and resources (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2016; Marmol, 2019; Sarabia & Collantes, 2020).

Teachers are overburdened with teaching and ancillary duties such as department head, curriculum head, program coordinator, or focal person. The Department of Education (DepEd) categorized the teachers into classroom teachers without ancillary functions and teachers with ancillary functions. Some teachers have six-hour teaching days and two-hour teaching and classroom-related duties. As stipulated in the Magna Carta for Teachers or the Republic Act 4670, Section 13

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that, teachers engaged in actual classroom instruction shall not require to render more than six hours of primary teaching in a day to ensure their personal and professional welfare (Abulencia, 2015; Alegado, 2018; David, Albert & Vizmanos, 2019).

Moreover, ancillary services are defined as responsibilities assumed by teachers outside of the classroom for improved school performance, such as home visits, feeding programs, skill remediation, enhancement activities, coaching various contests, coordinators for multiple areas, counseling pupils, and mentoring co-teachers. However, teachers encountered problems relative to the delivery of ancillary services because of time constraints, unfinished competencies, and financial woes (Machimura, 2015; Alhija, 2015; Abarro, 2018).

Furthermore, the recurrently overworked state of public-school teachers in the Philippines is well-known as the workload which is limited to teaching and other non-teaching tasks. Given this workload, actual teaching is increasingly being sidelined along with many other responsibilities and roles that teachers play. In fact, a recent study of Retubada in 2014 mentioned that, teachers in Davao del Sur, Region XI, had encountered problems with multiple ancillary functions. The Department of Education vowed to lessen teachers' workload; however, this remained unclear. On this note, teachers also experience positive gains from their experiences with ancillary functions, which challenge them to aspire more advancement for themselves (Retubada, 2014; David, Albert & Vizmanos, 2019; Mateo, 2018; Into & Gempes, 2018).

Thus, in this study, I looked into proficient teachers in South Fatima District handling multiple ancillary functions with at least years of teaching experience or longer both in elementary and secondary schools. Therefore, in this context, as a researcher, I am interested in knowing the experiences of these teachers as this can raise concern to the intended recipients of the study and come up with the implication for practice.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Despite the mandate in the Magna Carta for Teachers or Republic Act 4670 which stated that, teachers should engage in an actual classroom instruction shall not require more than six hours of primary teaching a day. Yet, handling multiple ancillaries, teachers tend to render exigencies on the service and spend more time working than the regular hours. Teaching with these ancillary functions is very demanding. However, it is best to explore the usual experiences of the teachers handling multiple ancillary functions. An in-depth understanding of their experiences and uncovering their reality may somehow form part of the department's decisions to implement more relevant policies and even amendments of such endeavors.

1.2 Purpose Statement

The purpose of this study was to describe the performance of the purposively selected elementary and secondary teachers handling multiple ancillary functions in the Division of General Santos City, specifically in the South Fatima District. In this study, ancillary functions were defined as non-teaching working loads of the teachers but school-related work that helped improve the school performance.

This study explored the experiences of the teachers handling multiple ancillary functions. Moreover, I let the participants of this study re-lived in their minds the experiences they had as elementary and junior high school educators and listen to the stories they would tell.

The recorder was utilized extensively during the in-depth interview, in addition to the written comments gathered. Various reports about the stories they planned to tell were grouped to form themes; these were the everyday experiences of the participants. Thus, in-depth interviews opened them to recall stories that would be utilized and recorded.

In addition, this multiple case study research was intended to help me understand and expand an in-depth understanding of the experiences of public elementary and junior high school teachers. In the same way, as this will be read by many, this will help the readers and participants examine their own extraordinary experiences and encourage them to understand their walk of life better.

1.3 Research Question

The research question was designed to lead the investigation to achieve the study's goal: How do teachers' performance handling multiple ancillary functions be described?

1.4 Theoretical Lens

Hertzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959) and the Expectancy Theory (1964) were anchored in this present study. These theories were considered in this study as they envelop the hypothetical underpinnings on teachers' experiences with multiple ancillary functions (Akhtar, Javed, & Iqbal, 2017).

Psychologist Frederick Herzberg developed Hertzberg's Two-Factor Theory in the 1950s. Herzberg identified two sets of factors in deciding employees working attitudes and level of performance, named Motivation & Hygiene Factors. Motivation factors are intrinsic factors that will enhance employees' job satisfaction, while Hygiene factors are extrinsic factors to prevent employee dissatisfaction. In addition, Two-Factor theory is strongly related to Maslow's hierarchy of needs, but it created more reasons to measure how individuals are interested in the workplace. Also, these two categories differ fundamentally and are independent of one another (Yusoff, Sanjeev & Surya, 2016; Andersson, 2017, Hur, 2018).

As discussed by Bevins in Herzberg's original study in 2018, he identified six Motivator factors that are determined intrinsically by the employee. They include recognition, achievement, the possibility of growth, development, responsibility, and the work itself. Motivators are described as "job content" due to the intrinsic nature of what is gained from motivators. Motivation among workers involves an encouraging work environment, which does not happen by chance. Addressing the elements that influence employee job satisfaction and then devising interventions that managers can undertake to integrate and increase those factors can result in a productive atmosphere (Sanjeev & Surya, 2016; Bevins, 2018; Alrawahi, Sellgren, Altouby, Alwahaibi & Brommels 2020).

On the other hand, motivation is the driving factor behind all human endeavors and is necessary for all human accomplishments. Victor Vroom's Expectation Theory in 1964 is one of the process theories of motivation. According to theory, the strength of an anticipation act would result in a given consequence. The appeal of that outcome to an individual determines the intensity of inclination to act in a particular way. Organizational rewards or job outcomes can help them to achieve these unique goals. As a result, the connection between corporate rewards or job outcomes and personal objectives is significant, especially how well organizational tips support an employee's objectives and how appealing they are. The employee's value on the work results illustrates this relationship (Osabiya, 2015; Robescu & Iancu, 2016; Lloyd & Mertens, 2018). These theories were relevant to the study's research undertaking as they consider teachers' work performance both in teaching and ancillary functions. The theories implied that work can be productive when both motivator and hygiene factors are improved. According to this view, teachers may be motivated if they feel appreciated and encouraged, also, they realize that they may grow and improve by taking on various work duties. Additionally, to prevent the job attrition of the teachers in the field, they must feel an assurance that they are treated right, with the best possible working conditions and fair compensation (Daniels, 2016; Wiyono, 2018; Cansoy 2019).

Moreover, to make a point, hygiene factors include achievement, recognition, responsibility, work itself, advancement, company policies and administration, technical supervision, working conditions, interpersonal relationship with supervisors, and salary. To boost workplace productivity, one must constantly consider the two elements by improving self-motivation and efficacy (Osabiya, 2015; Daniels, 2016; Cansoy, 2019).

2. METHOD

2.1 The Rationale for the Qualitative Approach

The current study used a qualitative research design, specifically a multiple case study and mainly adopted a case study design by Stake (1995). Case study research is a qualitative approach in which the investigator discovers real-life, contemporary bounded, or multiple fixed systems over time via thorough in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information and reports a case description and case themes through the unit of analysis of various cases or a single issue. Specifically, this present study was a joint or multiple case study wherein it consisted of various instances in which I examined several cases (Yazan, 2015; Ponelis, 2015; Gaikwad, 2017).

Various research proponents defined a case study; it provided a methodological approach in conducting this qualitative research tradition as Yazan (2015) refers to Yin (2002), illustrated qualitative case study as a study of the originality and complexity of a single case, coming to know its activity within necessary circumstances. It is an empirical investigation into an issue or matter by addressing how or why inquiries of phenomenon were interesting. On the other hand, Merriam

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(1998) elaborated that a qualitative case study is a thorough, holistic description and analysis of a constrained phenomenon such as a program, an institution, a person, a process, or a social unit. Further, a case study provides a means for emphasizing and extracting practical principles and methods for creating and expediting progress in solving real problems in the community (Dasgupta, 2015; Ponelis, 2015; Edwards, 2020).

As a researcher, I chose to follow the design and procedures presented by Stake (1995) over those offered by Yin (2002) and Merriam (1998) because it takes a more flexible approach and, while concerned with rigor in the processes, maintains a focus on what is studied, the case, rather than how it is deliberate, the method. The design and procedure proposed by Stake allow conducting the study existentially. The initial setup, as suggested, concerns the issues and issue questions, which led to the creation of the research questions. Stake's account highlights the significance of the researcher's skills to carry out qualitative research (Miles, 2015; Ridder, 2017; Gaikwad, 2017).

I also found Stake's case study more researcher-friendly than the others since it provides less extensive research paradigms that explore the experiences in a constructive and progressive approach. Aspects of Stake's case study design and methodology that are not prescriptive and unrestrictive are advantageous to me as a researcher. The case study design by Stake embodies an approach that is qualitative and closely aligned with a constructivist and interpretive orientation as a strong motivation underpins it for discovering meaning and understanding of experiences in context (Yazan, 2015; Gentles, Charles, Ploeg & McKibbin, 2015; Ridder 2017).

2.2 Samples and Site

The research participants in this study were the teachers who experienced multiple ancillary services; additionally, the primary purpose of this case study was to look into how well teachers teach when they were in charge of a range of supplementary services. I chose participants who have extensive experience with this phenomenon, considering their years of service, the number of ancillary services provided over time, the ratio of ancillary services to teaching loads, and maturity in handling both teaching and ancillary functions responsibilities. Also, I considered their willingness to participate in this study because I had generated substantial information for the case analysis.

In selecting the participants in this study, I employed purposeful sampling. It involved identifying and selecting individuals or groups that are exceptionally knowledgeable about or experienced with a particular phenomenon or interest (Palinkas et al., 2015). Furthermore, the participants of this study were six (6) permanent teachers from both elementary and junior high school teachers of South Fatima District in the Division of General Santos City with three or more ancillary loads and at least five years in service. These teachers have experience-rich attributes to provide important information regarding the study's purpose; also, the participants were selected regardless of their rank, age, and gender (Palinkas, Horwitz, Green, Wisdom, Duan & Hoagwood, 2015).

2.3 Access and Permission

In conducting this case study, I considered and constituted protocols to secure the ethical and social aspects of the research undertakings. The researcher received permission to conduct the study from the General Santos City Division Office and the participants' schools.

After which, they sent letters of invitation to participate among the identified participants of the study. When the participants consented to the request, data collection commenced.

The researcher explained the study's objective to the participants and obtained their consent to record their responses for analysis and interpretation, assuring them that their responses would be kept in strict confidence.

Participants were informed about their role in the study and the extent to which they were involved. There should be no personal interest of the researcher to any qualitative personal accounts.

2.4 Data Gathering Strategies

Following are the methods or undertakings that were done and observed during data collection, after obtaining approval, and after inspecting the guide questions thoroughly to guarantee the study instrument's suitability and validity.

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First, I prepared the necessary materials or requirements, including the venue and audio or voice recorder. The venue and time were ready during the first visit with the participants and extended the purposeful observations to gather firsthand information about people and places at a research site

Second, before the interview, the participants were given a copy of the consent form to sign. It contained the objectives of the study, the approaches, methodology, confidentiality, and benefits, including the contact number of the researcher. If ever there were clarifications or verifications of the purpose, the participants were encouraged with utmost opportunity to ask. They were retrieving consent forms with no further queries or clarifications. The said form indicates that the agreement is not just for research purposes but becoming a partner working with the participant as co-researcher.

Third, I transcribed the audio recordings after the interview process and utilized the member checking as a method of validation, whereby participants read and affirm the contents of the interview transcripts and affix their signature on them. Such a validation process signaled the trustworthiness of the data. Lastly, the researcher utilized multiple data sources as a part of the data gathering procedure, such as interviews, documents, and observations.

2.5 Data Analysis Approach

In this case study, the analysis focused on a specific case component. Data analysis was detailed in the description and consisted of analysis of themes through thematic analysis. A typical structure for data analysis in a case study consists of the following phases from Stake (1995) that were used in this study:

Description. It entailed the development of a detailed description of each instance of the case and its setting. I derived and described the experiences specific to the occasion; these were noted to draw themes for further analysis.

Categorical Aggregation. It involved collecting themes from the data, looking for the relevant meaning of the case to emerge. I collectively derived the common themes from the experience to categorize them accordingly.

Within-Case Analysis. This phase identified themes that emerged from data collected from each instance of the case, including connections between the articles. Verbatim passages and direct quotations used these themes to elucidate each piece. It served as the summary of the thematic analysis for the individual participant.

Cross-Case Analysis. This phase involves the thematic analysis across the cases that emerged from the within-case analysis. I examined themes across issues to discern common and different themes to all matters.

Interpretive Phase. In the final phase, I created the naturalistic generalizations from the data and reported the lesson learned from the case study (Yazan, 2015; Gentles, Charles, Ploeg & McKibbon, 2015; Ridder, 2017).

3. RESULT

3.1 Description of Participants

Participant 1 is an Elementary School Teacher 1 from Shuttle Elementary School. She has been teaching for ten (10) years. She has been handling three ancillaries for five years.

Participant 2 is an Elementary School Teacher 1 from Aspang Elementary School. He has been teaching for six (6) years and handling five ancillaries.

Participant 3 is an Elementary School Teacher 1 from Datal Salvan Elementary School for five years. She has been handling six (6) ancillaries for five years.

Participant 4 is a Secondary School Teacher 1 from Maligaya High School. He has been teaching for five (5) years and handling three ancillaries.

Participant 5 is a Secondary School Teacher 1 from Datu B. Balunto High School. She has been a Math teacher teaching for seven (7) years and handling five ancillaries since then.

Participant 6 is a Secondary School Teacher 1 from Datu B. Balunto High School. She is a guidance designate and has been teaching for seven (7) years. She has been handling eight (8) ancillaries for seven (7) years.

3.2 Analysis of Themes

This part merged the themes that described their experiences in handling multiple ancillary functions. These are the main findings of this research: How do the participants’ performance handling multiple ancillary functions be described?

Table 1: Multiple Ancillaries Handled by Elementary and Secondary School Teachers

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Elementary Teachers	
Reading Coordinator, English Coordinator, and Solid Waste Management Science Coordinator, YES-O, School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP), LRMDS, and SPG	Handled three or more ancillaries
School Guidance, EBEIS/ICT Coordinator, SBM Coordinator, LAC Coordinator, and Science Coordinator	
Secondary Teachers	
LAC coordinator, Guidance Coordinator, and Academic Coordinator	Handed-down responsibility
ICT Coordinator, Math Coordinator, Adopt a School Partnership Coordinator, GAD coordinator, and Brigada eskwela coordinator	
Guidance Counsellor Designate, NDEP Coordinator, GAD Coordinator, Oplan Balik Eskwela Coordinator, TSG Adviser, CGAP Coordinator	
Elementary Teachers	
Principal’s decision	Handed-down responsibility
The principal chose her.	
Turned-over	
Secondary Teachers	
Principal’s decision	Handled five or more years
Given by principal	
Decision of principal	
Elementary Teachers	
Five years	Handled five or more years
Six years	
Five years	
Secondary Teachers	
Five years	
Seven years	
Seven years	

This study unveils the teachers’ experiences handling multiple ancillary functions in South Fatima District. Mainly, the investigation dissected these experiences into details, which led to formulating emergent themes in Table 1.

Multiple Ancillaries Handled by Teachers

Handled Three or More Ancillaries

Both participants from elementary and secondary schools in South Fatima District handled three or more ancillaries. These teachers were from small schools with only three to fifteen teaching workforce. They have divided these ancillaries evenly by the number of teachers over the number of ancillaries they have to handle—about 26 coordinator-ships categorized as a heavy, medium, and light workloads.

Through memorandum No. 291, s. 2008, the Department of Education (DepEd) has provided its guidelines for implementing the Civil Service Commission (CSC) resolution on working hours for public school teachers, which states that a public school teacher shall give at most six hours of actual classroom teaching and two hours of teaching-related activities and duties, as follows: preparation of lesson plans; the practice of exercises, checking and recording of academic performances; conduct research; attendance to seminars, counseling; conference with parents; performance of coordination activities and community social services; participation in the preservation and improvement of school facilities; and, other related activities. However, a teacher is needed to work longer than six hours in the classroom or more than eight hours in

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a day due to the exigencies of the service, and additional payment will be calculated (Into & Gempes; 2018; Ancho & Bongco, 2019; Marmol, 2019).

The participants handled three or more ancillaries depending on the number of teachers per school; these teachers belong to small schools that do not take more workloads than ordinary teachers. These teachers demonstrate commitment and passion in teaching. Despite the multiple ancillaries they have handled, their firm will and desire made them stay in their profession.

Handed-down Responsibilities

Elementary and secondary public-school teachers were very responsible in doing their duties; they handled three or more ancillaries for more than five years. The school heads trusted them because they were given these ancillaries and believed in their potential and capacities. These teachers handle their duties effectively and efficiently. They empowered and promoted leadership skills to these teachers, resulting of being motivated and committed to taking these multiple ancillary functions over the years.

It indicates that these educators are dedicated and enthusiastic about their jobs. Their dedication to their careers fuels their drive, passion, and inspiration. To be a successful educator, one must be dedicated to both his students and the teaching profession as a whole.

Being entrusted by their school heads, elementary and secondary school teachers have handled multiple ancillaries for five or more years. According to researchers, empowerment implies real improvements in employees' professional authority and behavior, evident in their expanded autonomy and participation in broader organizational problems outside their routine task. They enhance teachers' autonomy by providing resources to become more active in programs and responsibilities (Balyer, Ozcan, & Yildiz, 2017; Lee & Nie, 2017; Fauza; 2020).

Handled Multiple Ancillaries for Five or More Years

Participants in the South Fatima district's elementary and secondary schools managed several ancillaries for five years. It implies that these teachers are committed to handling multiple ancillary functions. Their school administrators handed these ancillaries whether they had prior knowledge or not.

For more than five years, the participants were in charge of several supplementary duties; their dedication determines teachers' commitment to engaging regularly and doing their tasks effectively; it demonstrates that these teachers are skilled in dealing with these ancillaries. It also exhibits that these educators are committed to the responsibilities at hand. Teachers have critical role in maintaining school culture and academic performance. Teachers' commitment is a crucial factor in the success of schools since solid leadership leads to high levels of teacher commitment (Raman, Cheah, Don, Daud, & Khalid, 2015; Jovanovica & Ciricb, 2016; Celik & Yildiz, 2017).

Table 2: Teachers' Experiences on Pre and Post Handling of Multiple Ancillary Functions

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Elementary Teachers	
Worried Adjustment Difficult	Challenged
Secondary Teachers	
Difficult Challenging Very hard	
Elementary Teachers	
Mixed emotions Multi-tasking Enjoyed	Enjoyment
Secondary Teachers	
Challenging Fulfilling	
Elementary Teachers	

Pressured Versatile Secondary Teachers	Intrapersonal effect
Change in approach Sacrifice Elementary Teachers	Interpersonal effect
Healthy communication Teamwork Inspiration Secondary Teachers	Teamwork
Act as a bridge Good relationship Teamwork	

In table 2, participants from South Fatima District’s elementary and secondary schools place to the test in handling multiple ancillary functions firsthand. They are having a hard time adapting to their new responsibilities. As a result, after years of taking these ancillaries, they enjoyed and found it fulfilling. These ancillaries had an intra- and interpersonal influence and improved their teamwork through open communication with their school heads and colleagues (Lee & Li; 2015; Bashan & Holsblat, 2017; Wiyono, 2018).

Challenged

Elementary teachers felt worried and thought it was difficult to handle multiple ancillary functions firsthand. The preconception on taking extra ancillaries is to meet the expectations of the school head. These expectations might cause stress and interfere with work-life balance. On the other hand, secondary instructors felt overburdened because they were responsible for three ancillaries. Excessive workloads put personal human capabilities to the test, resulting in tension, uneasiness, irritation, and aggravation (Huyghebaert, Gillet, Beltou, Tellier, & Fouquereau, 2018).

Teachers’ attitude before taking on various ancillary functions, on the other hand, altered throughout time. Both elementary and secondary teachers viewed their students differently due to their anxiety and challenges. Despite feeling stressed at times due to a large backlog of work, they continue to do their best to complete their tasks; they have enjoyed and felt fulfilled in handling these ancillaries.

Moreover, they divided teachers’ workload into teaching duties, extra and co-curricular duties, interaction with stakeholders, and communication. Extreme workload has been found to predict emotional exhaustion, motivation to leave the teaching profession, and actual attrition, whereas supportive school environments are positively related to motivation to stay in the teaching profession (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2015; Nguse, 2015; Werang, 2018).

Enjoyment

At first, teachers both in elementary and secondary who were in charge of several ancillary roles felt uneasy. They have no thought what they are going to do. As time passes, they gain experience in performing multiple ancillary functions. They were familiar with the procedures they would be doing, and these roles turned out to be a challenge for them. It made them grow aside from teaching (Alhija; 2015; Baldwin & Bhavnani, 2015; Clipa, 2017).

Teachers’ jobs, which include several ancillary activities, are challenging in a fun way. To be productive and successful in their profession, they must devote additional time and effort. Even though they were tired, they had a good time.

To sum it up, despite the rigors of life as teachers handling multiple ancillary functions, they shared positive insights on their commitment and dedication. Both participants from elementary and secondary expressed positive feedback on their experiences handling various ancillary functions. Despite being challenged, they have learned and fulfilled their responsibilities (Clipa, 2017; Into & Gempes, 2018; Suchyadi, 2018).

Intrapersonal and Interpersonal Effect

Teachers’ intrapersonal and behavioral results are affected by their ability to manage various ancillary functions. Elementary teachers felt a little bit pressured due to the work they had to accomplish. However, these ancillaries made them versatile.

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They can manage to create reports and perform tasks given in a short period. On the other hand, secondary school teachers say that working multiple ancillaries affects dealing in class and among their peers.

Handling multiple ancillary functions has its intrapersonal and interpersonal effects on the participants. These ancillaries may have an impact on their emotional health as well as their relationships with pupils and colleagues. Collaborative work has likely to motivate teachers, reduce workloads, and boost self-efficacy. Furthermore, a study of Canadian elementary school teachers found that long work hours and difficult working circumstances led to teachers' mental health, stress, and burn-out (Alhija, 2015; Vangrieken, Dochy, Raes & Kyndt, 2015; Kutsyuruba, Walker, Stasel, & Al Makhmreh, 2019).

Teamwork

Teachers developed positive relationships with their peers on the elementary and secondary levels; they share their sentiments. The story of encouragement they receive from those around them will help them cultivate a positive mindset and grow personally. These ancillaries act as a bridge for them to work together, have healthy communication and help them to build teamwork.

The advantages of teamwork in the classroom are numerous. Cooperation can reduce workplace mistakes, increase employee and client satisfaction, and create opportunities for professional growth. More significant student effects, teacher preparation, teacher engagement, entrepreneurial activity, and improved student success are linked to teacher collaboration (Hwang & Anh, 2015; Ronfeldt, Farmer, McQueen & Grissom, 2015; Ballangrud, 2017).

Teachers are counting support from their colleagues and there with their school heads. Teamwork increases their morale and resilience in coping with difficult experiences, mainly ancillary functions. A rigid support system and positive relationships with the people around them would establish open communication within the school community (Moran, 2015; Balyer, 2017; Newburgh, 2019).

Table 3: Teachers' Resilience on Handling Multiple Ancillary Functions

Clustered Themes	Emergent Themes
Elementary	
Seek advice Knowledge Family	Faith and Trust
Secondary Family Relationship with God Support system	
Elementary Teachers	
Innovation Acknowledgment Improvement	Positive development
Secondary Teachers Different pieces of training Broaden the understanding Exposed into different organizations	
Elementary Teachers	
Optimism Manageability Eagerness	Persistence
Secondary Teachers Eagerness Manageability Enjoyment	

Along with the challenges encountered by the participants handling multiple ancillary functions, these teachers have developed their coping strategies and have their coping mechanisms. Both participants from elementary and secondary teachers rely on their support system particularly their family, co-teachers, and peers. Other participants relied on their faith, believing that they were destined to handle those challenges. Also, seminars and training helped them develop their innate

strengths and capabilities. Over time, they created these powers and skills, and they became exceptional teachers capable of handling a variety of additional jobs.

Teachers handling multiple ancillary roles recognize that their tasks are complex. The participants could develop their skills through innovations and training despite the challenges. Their persistence in addressing multiple ancillary functions shows their eagerness, optimism, and commitment (Hong, 2017; Gordon, 2018; Khan, 2019).

Faith and Trust

The coping mechanisms developed by the teachers were factors for them to get by with the challenges. Teachers with good faith realized their philosophy in education that directs to greater job fulfillment and retention to the profession. It also incorporates living in harmony, promoting a positive educational atmosphere and strong bonds amongst coworkers. These coping mechanisms provide more excellent emotional support for the teachers' stress and anxiety in handling excessive workloads (Moran, 2015; Hong, 2017; Newburgh, 2019).

Teachers relying on guidance and reassurance from their school head, colleagues, and peers and love and encouragement from family and friends developed a support system as a coping strategy for teachers handling multiple ancillary functions. People who develop open contact with others are often well-liked and welcomed, and as a result, they are happier and less troubled at work. It is the idea to foster healthy relationships and promote resilience in one's life, resulting in greater adaptability to deal with life's challenges. Attachment style is also a deciding factor in the perception of social support, which is linked to coping. Having a sound support system would lead to positive relationships with others and satisfaction with help (Jacobson, 2016; Ho & Chan, 2017; Maslyn, Schyns & Farmer, 2017).

Furthermore, research of Alhija in 2015 revealed that the teachers are exposed to various sources of stress, including workloads. To cope with these challenges, teachers discuss their problems with their family members, peers and take training and programs for personal development and resilience (Alhija, 2015; Nguse, 2015; Sandilos, Goble, Rimm-Kaufman & Pianta, 2018).

Positive Development

The essence of handling multiple ancillary functions to the participants on both elementary and secondary teachers made them gain positive developments and persistence. These teachers taking numerous ancillaries are motivated by their emotional and professional growth. Despite the difficulties these participants have encountered, they encourage teachers who handle excessive workloads. It implies that the participants show resilience in taking multiple ancillary functions.

Teachers represent schools, and they are accountable for various essential activities related to grooming youth as valued members of society. The teacher's workload is divided into teaching duties, extra and co-curricular duties, administrative, interaction with stakeholders, and communication. Both participants from elementary and secondary teachers view the life of a teacher handling multiple ancillary functions positively. They become more understanding and innovative in handling these ancillaries (Nguse, 2015; Balyer, 2017; Abarro, 2018).

The Department of Education has provided its guidelines for implementing Civil Service Commission resolution on working hours for public school teachers through memorandum No. 291, s. 2018 states that a public school teacher shall render at most six hours of actual classroom teaching and two hours of teaching-related activities and duties (Into & Gempes; 2018; Ancho & Bongco, 2019; Marmol, 2019).

Persistence

Overworked teachers have become a source of concern for teacher organizations. The Teachers' Dignity Coalition and the Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) in the Philippines issued separate statements urging the Department of Education to review teacher workloads to ensure their physical and mental health. Additionally, ACT went on to say that over time, teachers' workloads have become increasingly burdensome and demanding due to the introduction of policies that required a lot of effort and the "non-implementation of those that ensure adequate rest." (Hernando-Malipot, 2018; Ancho & Bongco, 2019; Cabisgas, 2019).

Teachers find ways to get the job done because their workload is based on national standards of teacher efficiency, which will later act as the basis for their performance assessment. In the recent study of Into and Gempes in 2018, teachers possess

optimism and positivity. They took the responsibilities through proper planning and time management. Despite challenges, they shared positive insights about their experiences on commitment and dedication, being positive, prospects for growth and development, and as a testament of faith and trust in one's ability (Moran, 2015; Into & Gempes, 2018; Cansoy, 2019).

3.3 General Findings

The participants in both elementary and secondary schools who handled multiple ancillary functions were entrusted by their school heads. They have been taking these ancillaries for more than five years. Despite their difficulties, they remain optimistic and resilient through thorough development, having a solid support system, and managing their time correctly to have a work-life balance (Nguse, 2015; Balyer, 2017; Abarro, 2018).

Six motivators were presented to boost employees' job satisfaction in Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory and Expectancy Theory, on which the current study was based. These are; recognition, achievement, the possibility of growth, advancement, responsibility, and the work itself. Motivation among employees requires an encouraging work environment by addressing job satisfaction factors. It is evident in this study that these factors are present, which made the participants resilient with handling multiple ancillary functions (Yusoff, Sanjeev & Surya, 2016; Andersson, 2017, Hur, 2018).

Moreover, being empowered on handling multiple ancillaries by their school head made them more confident in managing their responsibilities. These teachers share authority and responsibilities with their school heads., employees' empowerment improves employees' management and behavior. Grant made the participants more dedicated to their responsibilities fuels their drive, passion, and inspiration (Moran, 2015; Balyer, 2017; Newburgh, 2019).

Additionally, recognition from school heads and colleagues made the participants feel more appreciated and motivated to handle multiple ancillary functions. Table 3 addressed that teachers' well-being is related to a positive relationship with students, colleagues, and families. These factors help teachers develop resilience by addressing the challenges in the teaching workplace. The participants feel fulfilled in performing multiple ancillary functions after being recognized by their school heads and colleagues (Hong, 2017; Gordon, 2018; Khan, 2019).

Furthermore, motivation plays a vital role in handling multiple ancillary functions for a long time. The participants in both elementary and secondary schools were more satisfied than frustrated. Those confident in their professions are more likely to complete their duties on time and follow the school's goals. The feeling of pleasure and delight that comes from carrying out one's responsibilities and commitments is characterized as job satisfaction for teachers (Balyer, Ozcan & Yildiz, 2017; Cansoy, 2019; Fauza, 2020).

4. DISCUSSION

This section summarizes the study's emerging topics and analysis. It tells the stories and experiences of teachers tasked with doing various supplementary activities while carrying out their duties. This chapter discusses the essential findings in the South Fatima District when it comes to many auxiliary tasks.

4.1 The Case of Elementary School Teachers

The Elementary School Teachers were described through the following: EST 1 as passionate; EST 2 as versatile and diligent, and EST 3 as strategic and proud elementary school teacher. These teacher-participants show commitment as well as enthusiasm in handling multiple ancillary functions. They have experienced the same challenges in managing these ancillaries, yet they cope differently. Family, colleagues, and being diligent in managing of such ancillaries are their coping mechanisms.

They were encouraged and motivated to improve their knowledge and skills through these ancillaries. They feel motivated every time they have accomplished their school heads, and colleagues recognize their programs, activities, and efforts. Thus, handling multiple ancillary functions made these teacher-participants committed, enthusiastic, strategic, and motivated.

4.2 The Case of Secondary School Teachers

The secondary school teachers were described as the following: SST 1 as ever-patient and job-oriented, SST 2 as eager to serve with integrity and being optimistic, and SST 3 as loving and selfless secondary school teacher. These teacher-participants from secondary schools were job-oriented in handling multiple ancillary functions. They perform these tasks

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because they were entrusted to do so. Having their integrity in the department made these teachers committed to the jobs they have handled. They were inspired not just by their school leaders but also by the students and their growth.

They see managing various ancillary duties as more than just a duty to be performed; it's a way for them to advance professionally. Their potential has been refined through training and seminars that have provided them with information and abilities. As a result, these instructors were committed to their responsibilities and felt satisfied and fulfilled whenever their school heads and colleagues recognized and supported them.

4.3 Concluding Remarks

Teachers handling multiple ancillary roles were gathered from the results of this study which showed that the majority of the participants gained positive benefits from their experiences, challenging them to strive for more extraordinary advancement to become better educators despite the rigors of life. The study found that teachers handling multiple ancillary functions are even more inspired despite of many difficulties. Understanding their difficulty as a teacher added to the body of education information. Their attitude toward their personal and professional well-being would change if they valued the importance of resilience in the teaching profession.

As a teacher, I have noticed that teachers who perform multiple ancillary functions have unique attitudes, abilities, and beliefs that set them apart from other educators. They demonstrated to all educators how to value fortitude and reinforce their engagement in all facets of their professional lives. Multiple ancillary functions of teachers have significant benefits in terms of personal and professional growth. It also has a broader impact on all educators throughout the world. Despite being given a more comprehensive array of teaching-related responsibilities, they had used it as a reference in developing their skills and strengthening their organizational commitment to public service. They understood the value of time management and their primary role as teachers, increasing students' academic performance.

Moreover, this research makes accessible to the general public the experiences and perspectives of teachers with several ancillary roles and the contexts extracted from the results. Understanding the real-life experiences of teachers with multiple ancillary functions led to new possibilities and proposals for future studies on multiple ancillary tasks in the educational setting.

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